

The effect of macroscopic quantum interference between two Josephson junctions connected in a superconducting circuit, first demonstrated in 1964, is of great practical importance.

Digital noise is present to a greater or lesser extent in all digital photographs, appearing in the form of individual damaged pixels, deteriorating the image quality. It is customary to identify four main causes of digital noise.

First of all, it is necessary to isolate photon noise associated with fluctuations in the number of photons counted by individual pixels of the matrix. The appearance of photon noise is most noticeable in shaded areas of the image and at insufficient shutter speed. The signal-to-noise ratio is maximum at low intensity of the main lighting.

The second important factor in the occurrence of digital noise is associated with heating of the matrix in the active state (during a long exposure) and leads to dark current noise.

The third type of noise is associated with the amplifiers used by manufacturers, which results in a recorded pattern of damaged pixels.

The fourth reason may be damage to the camera matrix, associated with burnout of individual pixels and mechanical defects of the lenses. The intensity of noise caused by the first three reasons, as a rule, does not exceed 5%.

The presence of digital noise leads to both a deterioration in the overall appearance of the image and additional difficulties in its processing. Algorithms for image segmentation and edge detection, which work well in the absence of noise, lead to amplification of damaged pixels.

Problems that arise when processing noisy images are usually solved by first using anti-aliasing filters. However, anti-aliasing filters, by reducing the intensity of damaged pixels, lead to blurring of contours, which significantly complicates further image segmentation and search for contours in the image.

In this regard, the urgent task is to develop specialized algorithms for solving problems of segmentation and contour extraction. Also relevant is the task of identifying and correcting damaged pixels.

The problem of digital image clustering arises when solving a fairly wide range of applied problems, such as processing sensing results, processing medical and biological images, functioning of computer vision systems, authentication problems, pattern recognition and others.

At the same time, methods based on searching for areas of uniform filling do not give good enough results for images containing unclear contours and areas of gradient color changes.

Most modern software tools solve the problem of selecting individual image areas in an interactive mode, shifting a significant part of the task of searching for individual clusters in the image to the user. In addition, the user is asked to manually configure a number of parameters. In this connection, the urgent task is to develop algorithms that perform image clustering automatically with a minimum number of customizable parameters.

The problem of identifying pixels in digital images that are damaged by digital noise of random color is relevant when transmitting information over a noisy channel, damage to information storage media and defects in devices for receiving graphic information.

Despite the fact that this task is quite easy to solve manually, automating this process causes certain difficulties. This circumstance is due to the fact that the task of identifying damaged pixels can be reduced to the problems of pattern recognition during unsupervised learning.

The development of algorithms that detect damaged pixels automatically with maximum efficiency is relevant, since there are a fairly small number of methods that solve this problem.

The need to isolate contours in digital images arises in the process of solving a large number of problems related to the analysis of graphic objects. Today, most edge detection algorithms are based on differential operators.

However, this approach is unstable to point digital noise, which increases when differential operators are used. In this connection, the task of developing noise-resistant algorithms that detect contours in an image is relevant.

The nature of photon noise lies in the discrete nature of detection of the radiation flux by quantum detectors and reflects fundamental natural laws .

It is convenient to consider the statistical properties of the processes of registration of radiation and photon noise on the basis of the semiclassical theory of photo registration.

The convenience of the semiclassical approach lies in the classical consideration of electromagnetic fields, while in the quantum representation only the process of interaction of radiation with a photosensitive material is considered.

Since the study of random processes during the emission and propagation of electromagnetic waves is beyond the scope of this study, the consideration assumes the absence of spatiotemporal fluctuations in the radiation intensity.

The semiclassical theory is based on the following assumptions. The probability of a photoevent on an area of the photosensitive surface that is small compared to the area of light coherence, in a time shorter than the coherence time, is proportional to the wave intensity, the length of the time interval and the area of the photosensitive surface.

The probability of more than one photoevent in the considered time and area intervals is negligible compared to the probability of one photoevent and no photoevents. Photoevents in two non-overlapping time intervals are independent.

These assumptions correspond to the problem of statistics of discrete independent events, which has a solution in the form of a Poisson distribution.

Each pixel in a noisy image is the sum of the true pixel value and a random Gaussian distributed noise value.

Poisson noise is noise that occurs when there are not enough photons measured by the sensor to provide detectable statistical information. Therefore, it is also called “photon noise”.

This noise arises based on the nature of phenomena such as light and electric current, which consist in the movement of discrete packets (photons, electrons). If the number of particles carrying energy is small enough, then the uncertainty due to the Poisson distribution increases. The amount of Poisson noise increases with the average current or light intensity.

When recording a flux of high-intensity photons, the signal value will have a scatter of values that significantly exceeds the signal from a single photon, so the signal will be almost continuous. As the intensity of the photon flux decreases, the set of possible signal values will decrease.

The images obtained from such streams have a number of features. They have a noise-like character and pronounced discreteness. They almost completely lack areas of equal brightness. Such images, as a rule, are of little use for direct visual perception, and traditional quality criteria such as contrast and signal-to-noise ratio are ineffective.

Analysis of the dependences of the probability distribution shows that fluctuations in the number of registered photons in a pixel degenerate into a scatter of single photons across pixels at ultra-weak photon fluxes.

Since light has a quantum nature and with an average flux in a matrix pixel of less than unity, possible implementations of the registration process are reduced to two possible options:

photon registered (photoelectron generated);

the photon is not registered (no signal).

However, it can be assumed that in the chaotic distribution of single photons over the pixels of the frame, obtained with fluxes on average less than a photon per pixel, there is information about the image.

Assessing the information content of an image consisting of elements with pronounced intensity sampling up to binary requires a non-standard approach.

Digital imaging and processing devices are more compact, more technologically advanced, and have many advantages over analog ones, but they are also measuring equipment and have measurement errors.

The resulting digital image is the sum of the desired signal and noise. Mathematically, a digital image is a two-dimensional discrete sequence, which consists of the sum of the original non-noisy image and the noise component.

There are a number of unsolved problems in developing noise reduction methods for digital contrast images.

Lack of research on noise in digital contrast images. Noise models are often used in the form of white Gaussian noise with a constant noise component throughout the entire image, impulse noise, or a combination of both, without conducting a study of the noise distribution in a real digital image.

Noise and subsequent anti-aliasing greatly affect the contrast border of objects in the image, blurring it. Attention is not always paid to restoring contrast boundaries in the image.

The methods being developed are often configured to work with specific images, or the configuration occurs in a “manual” mode.

Image characteristics such as the level of noise in the image or the amount of contrast difference are not taken into account.

The basic element from which all computer images are constructed is the pixel. A pixel is the smallest addressable spatial display element capable of reproducing the full color range.

Any raster digital image is a collection of pixels. Pixels are arranged in rows and columns, forming a rectangular matrix.

It is worth noting that a string (sequence of characters) is one of the central objects of computer science. Any sequence, be it a sequence of bytes in a file or a sequence of words in text, is a string. In this sense, each algorithm operates on a string of bits representing the input data.

Naturally, such a general view of the nature of the processed data is not justified for all problems, but the range of issues operating with such an abstract representation is still very wide, because often the patterns in the source data are either too complex for formalization or are completely unknown.

As an example, we can cite the tasks of file compression, DNA sequence analysis, text search and many others. Algorithms that effectively solve such problems almost always explicitly or implicitly solve the problem of highlighting certain patterns in strings that are specific to that particular question.

Digital images are formed from an analog signal by digitizing it with an analog-to-digital converter (ADC). ADCs can convert various analog signals such as electromagnetic waves, sound waves, light, etc. In the case of images, visual information is digitized.

ADCs that convert light into a digital image are called photosensitive matrices. They consist of a large number of small light-sensitive sensors that are located on a substrate. Light-sensitive sensors capture and store photons of light that fall on them and are converted into electrical current. This current is the information carrier.

Receiving information from each sensor of the photosensitive matrix, the equipment forms an image. Due to various physical limitations, digital imaging devices cannot be perfect. Like many other measuring devices, digitizing an analog image introduces measurement errors.

As a result, the generated image contains a useful signal and digital noise, which is a mask of pixels of random color and brightness. To work with an image, you need to present it as some model that can be implemented on a computer.

A model is an abstract representation of reality in some form (for example, mathematical, physical, symbolic, graphical, or descriptive) designed to represent certain aspects of that reality and provide answers to the questions being studied.

The first source of noise is the light itself. Light is a stream of photons. Reflecting from objects and passing through the camera lens, photons hit the surface of the photosensitive matrix, which is essentially a photon counter. Due to the discrete nature of light, different photosensitive elements can detect different numbers of photons.

In the ideal case, when the camera does not introduce any distortion into the generated signal, its sensitivity depends only on photon noise. Photon noise is a random deviation in the number of photons relative to the average value. Due to the independence of photons in the light stream, the number of photons in a single selected area (pixel) in a particular frame is subject to Poisson statistics.

Photosensitive matrices, or photo matrices, have a certain level of signal that forms the final image. And the fewer photons hit the photomatrix, the more the signal has to be amplified in order to get an image.

The signal amplification factor is called photosensitivity. The light sensitivity of digital cameras is usually expressed in units equivalent to the ISO light sensitivity of gelatin-silver photographic emulsions. The higher the ISO, the higher the gain, the more noise there will be in the image.

In addition, noise in digital photo matrices is generated from the heating of photosensitive elements, interference in the signal transmission path, matrix production technology, etc.

Consequently, the amount of noise depends on: photon noise, the production technology of the digital matrix and the density of placement of individual photosensitive elements on it.

As a result, image noise will always be present in a digital image to some extent. Although digital imaging is relatively new, a large body of knowledge has already accumulated in this area.

However, some sources claim that noise in a digital image has a Gaussian distribution. Based on this, noise reduction methods are developed that require a Gaussian distribution of noise in the image. But no reliable studies were found that would confirm this fact.

The fact is that photosensitive matrices use sensors that record brightness, but not color. Color information is obtained by placing blue, red or green color filters in front of the sensors. The arrangement of such filters on the matrix can be different, but the most popular is called a Bayer filter or Bayer pattern.

The filter consists of 2x2 element squares, where one element is red, one blue and two green. The classic Bayer filter uses three color filters that the human eye can recognize. They are located in such a way that red and blue are adjacent to green vertically and diagonally.

Each cell contains twice as many green elements as red and blue elements; as a result, the resolution is maximum in the green region of the spectrum, which corresponds to the biological structure of the human retina.

When the light flux is digitized by a digital matrix, the image is projected onto light-sensitive diodes coated with color filters. The result is a mosaic of three color components. The final image obtained from the matrix is not the usual digital image that we see on a computer.

In the final image, each pixel contains only one color component of the projection of the real image onto the photo matrix by the lens. It turns out that the real color value can only be made up of four adjacent red, blue and two green pixels.

Thus, the GRBG pixel block approximately forms only one average pixel, which reduces the output resolution by 4 times. In order to maintain the true resolution of the photo sensor, the missing color components of each pixel are calculated based on information about the color of neighboring pixels.

The result of mathematical interpolation is presented as a 24-bit image, where 8 bits are used to encode a pixel for each of the three colors, or as they are otherwise called, channels in the RGB color model. This process is called demosaicing.

Also, the distribution of noise can be affected by the presence of various boundaries (contrast, color) in the image. Considering the fact that the brightness of pixels in a digital image is discrete and limited to 256 values, it is not clear how noise will behave at the boundaries of permissible values.

As an example of comparison, we can use the Huffman algorithm using the JPEG compression format as an example, since The principles of this particular standard are currently often used to eliminate intra-frame redundancy in a video information signal.

In the JPEG standard, entropy compression is the last step in image compression.

As you know, an image, when encoded to JPEG, is divided into blocks of 8x8 pixels, also called MCU (Minimum Codable Unit) blocks, which can be represented as 8x8 square matrices.

After the discrete cosine transform (DCT) procedure, such a matrix contains the values of the spectrum components of the MCU block that it represents. Each of the matrices is subjected to Huffman coding sequentially using one Huffman code table for all MCUs.

The Huffman code table shows the correspondence between the values of the spectrum components and the variable length codes (set of bits) that describe them. The JPEG codec can use standard tables to the JPEG standard specification, either generate an original table, or optimize a standard table taking into account the specifics of the encoded image signal.

In the first case, the operation of collecting statistical data on an image and forming a Huffman tree based on it is eliminated, which leads to a reduction in the computational load and a reduction in the time required to encode the image.

In other cases, at the expense of the number of calculations and encoding speed, the most efficient image compression is achieved due to the fact that the Huffman code table will be compiled taking into account the characteristics of the ensemble of encoded image signals.

To enable subsequent decoding of the image on the receiving side of the communication channel, Huffman code tables are introduced into the output signal of the encoder's digital stream. In this case, only the number of bits of variable-length codes and the values of matrix coefficients corresponding to these lengths are recorded in the transmitted table, and not the actual enumeration "bit string - coefficient value".

JPEG also provides for the use of arithmetic compression instead of Huffman coding, but it is used extremely rarely for a number of reasons related to the lack of support for this coding by most decoders and the presence of patent restrictions.

The end point for receiving a video information signal is the human visual system, which registers and processes this information, presenting it in the form of images. For this reason, when designing the latest video information systems or modifying existing ones, it is very important to take into account the characteristics of the human visual system.

Taking these features into account, it becomes possible to form a set of criteria for the fidelity of image reproduction at the output of a video information system and the decipherability of this image by a person.

The human visual system consists of the eyes, optic nerve and brain, the joint work of which ensures the formation of three-dimensional images of the surrounding world. The eye, like the lens of a television camera, is an optical receiver and is a delicate and complex mechanism.

The degree of accuracy of image formation in the brain will depend on the quality of the signal coming to the input of the receiver (in our case, the image signal), the consistency of its characteristics with the processing system of the receiver, and the accuracy of processing by this receiver.

In order to understand how to ensure consistency of the incoming signal with the characteristics of the eye, we will consider the main elements of the eye and the principle of their operation.

The human eye consists of such basic elements as the sclera, pupil, lens and retina. The sclera serves as the biological body of the eye, which contains the rest of the elements listed above.

The pupil is a diaphragm that regulates the amount of light transmitted. The lens is a lens that allows the eye to focus on objects. The retina can be described as a light-perceiving matrix, which consists of two types of active analyzing elements - rods and cones.

From physiological studies of the eye, it is known that the rods are activated in the dark or during twilight hours and perceive only shades of gray. Cones are involved in daytime vision, perceive color and, accordingly, their resolution is much higher than that of rods.

In addition, due to working under different conditions, the maximum sensitivity of rods and cones is achieved at different wavelengths. For this reason, the sensitivity of the human eye depends on the wavelength. The range of wavelengths in which the eye is capable of detecting signals is from 380 nm to 760 nm.

The greatest sensitivity, and therefore the resolving power of the eye, is achieved at a wavelength of 555 nm (green-yellow color), with daytime vision, and at a wavelength of 515 nm, with twilight vision. As you move away from this value, to both sides of the spectrum, the sensitivity of the eye drops and begins to tend to zero, starting with wavelengths of 380 nm - violet and 760 nm - red.

Everything that lies on both sides of the boundaries of this range is called ultraviolet and infrared radiation, respectively.

The spectral characteristic is the dependence of the spectral density of radiation power on the frequency (wavelength) of radiation. In relation to the human eye, the spectral characteristic is called the visibility curve.

Accordingly, for human vision, two visibility curves are distinguished - for day and night vision. Different observers have different visibility curves, so there is an average representation of them.

Because of the shift between the curves of daytime vision and night vision, the cones register blue-violet as a light shade of gray and red as a dark shade. This shift is called the Purkinje shift.

In addition, the value of the daytime sensitivity of the eye to radiation, for example, with a wavelength of 520 nm is absolutely identical to the sensitivity to radiation with a wavelength of 690 nm, and the value of the sensitivity of the eye to radiation with a wavelength of 480 nm is identical to the sensitivity to radiation with a wavelength of 630 nm.

Thus, objects with different brightness values may be perceived by the eye as equally bright, or exposure to equally bright objects, for example, with blue and green colors, will not be perceived equally.

In connection with the above, it can also be noted that, depending on the brightness recorded by the visual system, adaptation of the eye takes place. Adaptation occurs through manipulation of the size of the eye's pupil, as well as the transition from cone to rod vision or vice versa.

At the same time, there is dark adaptation, which means a transition from exposure to bright light to less bright light, and light adaptation - from dark to bright.

Rods have the greatest sensitivity to light, while, as already noted, they are not able to register color; their resolution is less than that of cones, due to the lower concentration of the former per unit area of the retina, although their total number is much higher than that of cones.

During light adaptation, the eye adjusts its characteristics much faster than during dark adaptation. If the light is too bright, which occurs in the mode when the eye is adapted to night vision and has the highest sensitivity, an unpleasant feeling of blindness appears, because irritation of the rods, due to the too rapid decomposition of the chemically active substance - rhodopsin, is extremely strong and the eye is blinded.

At the same time, the cones, which have not yet developed a protective mechanism in the form of the chemical melanin from too bright light, are also severely irritated.

The upper limit of blinding brightness depends on the time of dark adaptation of the eye, therefore, the longer dark adaptation occurred, the lower the brightness of the light causes blinding. If very brightly lit or blinding objects enter the field of view, they impair the perception of signals on most of the retina.

Only after sufficient time has passed, the adaptation of the eye to bright light ends and the eye begins to function normally. Full light adaptation reaches its maximum value after 8 - 10 minutes, with dark adaptation after 60 - 80 minutes.

Complete dark adaptation can be called long-term (tens of minutes); in addition to it, short-term (fractions and units of seconds) and medium-term (tens of seconds, minutes) can also be distinguished.

It can be noted that the dynamic range of the eye when adjusting to brightness levels is very wide, but there is also an inertia in adjustment, which becomes a very important factor taken into account when forming an image at the input and output of systems for generating and displaying video information signals.

In addition to the eye itself, the functioning of the brain also plays an important role in the visual system. Therefore, along with the elements and processes described above, one of the main features of vision is also feedback, which determines the specifics of the visual system.

In this case, the human brain not only processes incoming video information (video information processing unit), but also provides control of the visual system in video control mode via feedback circuits (optic nerve).

When the visual system operates, a restructuring of the characteristics of the visual system takes place depending on the control signals arriving at the individual elements of the presented structural diagram.

In an optical system, at least two elements with adaptive tuning should be distinguished. There is regulation of the aperture size and automatic restructuring of the plane of focusing of vision into the space of localization of the object subjected to video control.

The level of integral adaptation significantly affects the sensitivity and equivalent extent of the frequency characteristics of the visual system in the spatial, temporal and color directions, which determines the resolution of the eye in the corresponding direction.

It should be noted that there is a reverse trend in the regulation of these characteristics. Activation of sensitivity, which occurs with a decrease in the average illumination of monitored objects, is associated with an increase in the weight of the integral processing of video information and, consequently, with a decrease in the resolution of the eye in all directions (space, time and color directions).

In dynamic adaptation mode, the characteristics of the visual system are not optimized. As noted above, there are several areas of adaptive restructuring of the operating mode of the eye: short-term, medium-term, long-term.

The process of adaptation to average illumination is completed in approximately 30-40 minutes. Once adaptation is complete, vision performance is optimized for the specific video monitoring conditions.

For the visual system, the effects of differential video control are very specific in their effect on the observer. Classic experiments (Brock and Sulzer, 1902) proved that the visual system has different characteristics when perceiving screens with constant and short-term illumination.

It turned out that differential effects appear only at illumination levels greater than 30 lux. Due to the differential properties of perception, screens with short-term (≈ 0.05 sec) exposure were rated

by observers as having approximately 5 times greater illumination relative to the actual illumination (screen with constant illumination).

Thus, alternating long images of dimly lit scenes with short-term highlights causes discomfort. Let's consider the reasons for this phenomenon. In low light conditions, the sensitivity of the analyzing elements of the eye increases and the feedback circuit manages to adjust (increase) the size of the pupil (aperture).

Therefore, a short flash of screen illumination, in this case, is blinding.

Important elements of the functioning of the visual system are adjustments to the size of the pupil, the shape of the lens, interruption of the light flux, eye movements, tremor, adaptation phenomena, and the presence of an area of clear vision.

It is also necessary to take into account the presence in the visual system of spatial and color sampling of the input image by light-sensitive elements. At the same time, complete suppression of sampling distortions is ensured by choosing a certain distribution, a certain sensitivity and the size of the distributed photosensitive elements within the "clear vision" area and the periphery.

The sensitivity of the sampling element is determined not only by the illumination time, but also by its dimensions, which can also be adjusted. Therefore, observing dimly lit scenes is characterized by a combination of increasing sensitivity and decreasing the resolution of vision in frame space and, in the inter-frame and color directions.

The differential specificity of color perception is revealed by contrasting with additional colors. At the same time, tremor also determines the contrast of boundaries and small details when observing objects of a given color in relation to, for example, a background with an additional color.

Accordingly, discomfort for the observer may occur during short-term changes in the color of the image from reproduced to additional. The differential operating mechanism here is the same: when illuminated with a given color, the sensitivity of the elements to the additional color increases.

Elements of differential processing of video information may include tremor, image scanning, interruptions of light flow, eye movements, etc. The specificity here is the relative contrast of controlled objects due to discrete shifts of the "clear vision" area to adjacent areas of the controlled scene.

In this case, there are successive relaxation changes in the controlled video information with multiple returns to the controlled object. This ensures optimization of the differential perception characteristics inherent in the human visual system.

Elements of integral processing of video information are tracking moving objects, adjusting the size of the photosensitive element, fixing the eyes, the area of "clear vision", etc. The control of the visual system is implemented on the basis of the accumulation and classification of information characteristics of objects in a block of memory levels.

Video information accumulated by a person allows adaptive optimization of the characteristics of the visual system, eliminating the perception of unchanged or recognizable video information. On the other hand, interruptions in accumulated video information are also changes.

Feedback circuits stimulate the differential effect of “emphasizing the expected” video information in cases of its relatively long absence.

P.S.

The field of research into the effects of light on quantum systems and material environments is limitless, as are the topics of black holes and dark matter.

The emergence of a quantum computer is associated with a change in views on computing. If twenty years ago calculations were considered as an abstract logical procedure, now studies of the material implementation of the computing process are coming to the fore.

The very idea of a new paradigm was expressed back in 1960 by the American physicist R. Landauer, who said that calculations are implemented on devices operating on the basis of natural processes, and that to determine the fundamental limit of computability, you need to know the physical implementation.

A tendency is gradually emerging to consider quantum theory not as an ontology of the world, but only as a successful computing machine that predicts the probabilities of outcomes.

Before this paradigm shift, the progress of computer technology followed the path of a quantitative increase in computing power based on semiconductor devices. The quantum computer has given impetus to the development of a wide range of approaches to modeling the basic unit of a quantum computer, the qubit.

Implementations included various kinds of quantum systems - from trapped atoms and even large molecules, the state of which was controlled by changing an external magnetic field, to ring currents in a superconducting environment.

Practical interest in the creation of quantum computers arose after P. Shor’s proof in 1994 of the theorem on the possibility of fast factorization of large numbers using a quantum algorithm. To understand the significance of his discovery, it is necessary to talk about the role of this mathematical procedure in the modern Internet.

Information is transmitted from user to user in encrypted form; the main encryption algorithm is based on multiplying two large prime numbers. All cryptography is based on two inverse mathematical procedures, one of which is easy to perform (for example, multiplying numbers), and the second is difficult (for example, factoring into prime factors).

Encryption occurs with a public key, i.e. one of the prime numbers and encrypted information are transmitted in the public domain, and the receiving computer decrypts the received messages, factoring the received data (RSA technology).

Since it is difficult to factorize (this is a problem that can be solved by exhaustive search), the reverse calculation on ordinary computers takes a long time.

Therefore, investments were made in technologies for the development of quantum computers huge funds. The memory architecture itself follows the fundamental memory structure of a regular computer, in which the minimum unit is a bit - a memory cell that can take the value zero or one.

The memory cell of a quantum computer is called a qubit; its difference from a bit is that a qubit can also accept all intermediate values from zero to one. In addition, a quantum computer uses the principle of superposition, according to which a memory cell is in all states simultaneously, which allows parallel calculations.

There is also a difference in the number parameters involved. If a classical computer used only one property of an elementary particle - the charge of an electron, then a quantum computer uses a whole range of quantum numbers and the entanglement of an ensemble of particles.

There are major technological challenges standing in the way of creating a quantum computer. The quantum system, which is a qubit, is very unstable, quickly decays, which does not allow running long-term calculations on a quantum computer, and, in addition, the quantum system has low noise immunity, i.e. it is strongly affected by noise.

That's why The core of a quantum computer can only operate at ultra-low temperatures, when the interference coming from thermal vibrations of atoms is reduced and superconductivity takes place.

A quantum computer is a new way for microparticles to interact with human consciousness. In a quantum computer, elementary particles play an informational role in addition to the consciousness of the observer, going through several stages of evolution and maintaining their essence.

Eliminating the measurement procedure makes it possible not to raise questions related to a number of paradoxes of quantum mechanics. The issue of eliminating the influence of an observer on a quantum system is solved from the point of view of the information approach.

In the latter case, the role of human consciousness for a quantum object is that its material properties are converted into information. Determination arises only in our consciousness, but not in the object itself; consciousness does not act on the physical being as such, but on the superposition of possible states.

Apparently, we have too little data to discuss the problems of quantum gravity beyond the purely abstract formulation of the problem. However, there is one class of systems that allow one to obtain interesting results based on the most general principles of quantum mechanics and the theory of gravity. These are Black Holes and the processes of their quantum evaporation.

The application of quantum mechanics to Black Holes immediately led to the surprising conclusion that Black Holes must emit radiation. The radiation is obtained with good accuracy as thermal radiation, and assuming that ultimately the Black Hole will evaporate completely, we come to the paradoxical conclusion that almost all the information swallowed by the Black Hole during its life (and during its formation) has completely disappeared, contrary to the unitary the nature of quantum mechanical evolution.

The standard solution has become the assumption of the existence of a stretched horizon of Planck thickness, which can absorb, thermalize and re-emit information.

Of course, by virtue of the equivalence principle, a falling observer should not notice anything special at all when crossing the horizon, since the curvature of the horizon of a Black Hole of macroscopic mass is very small.

However, having discovered this remarkable fact of the absence of a physical membrane, the falling observer will no longer have a chance to transmit this information to a remote colleague, and thus we can avoid the contradiction by accepting the point of view of the principle of complementarity and abandoning the global description of all space-time within the framework of one effective theories of the kind we are familiar with.

Over the past few years, a huge number of works have been written on this topic with different points of view and proposals.

In particular, one can try to take the point of view of strong complementarity, which argues that it does not matter if two observers observe completely different physical reality in relation to the same physical system, if they do not even have the possibility in principle to communicate their results to each other.

This option does not seem to work (at least not without problems), because the falling observer may make very precise measurements of the early radiation before directly entering the zone (to clarify the issue of entanglement), or because he may change his mind and turn back , already in the zone, but before crossing the horizon.

However, it can be argued that the problematic measurements and conclusions turn out to be unrealistic in terms of computational complexity, require extreme precision akin to Maxwell's demon, completely change the state of the Black Hole itself, or practically correspond to the observation of quantum superpositions of macroscopic systems. The issue remains controversial, and new ideas could radically change our understanding of quantum mechanics and gravity.

Black Hole Physics is the only field today in which we can discuss the problems of quantum gravity beyond purely abstract and mathematical formulations.

Black Holes are remarkable objects of theory (and, apparently, not only of theory), which have never ceased to amaze us since the laws of their thermodynamics were discovered, a very unexpected event for such simple and, at first glance, structureless objects. Perhaps they are trying to tell us something about more fundamental physics.

Metaphysics:

If Claude Shannon chose the dimensionless unit of bits to measure information, then the Creator chose as a universal unit of measurement of information in space the universal plan of structure of any form of matter, regardless of its type and semantic content.

The Creator chose a quadrupole, two dipoles in their unity, as a universal measure of information. A magnetic dipole and an electric dipole, a memory structure and a sensitive system are a universal unit form of matter for measuring electromagnetic information brought by waves of a photonic medium.

The key to understanding the natural laws of nature that control the processes of growth and development of specific objects of the material world can be the electromagnetic method of interaction of matter (electronic shell) with the subtle matter of waves of the photonic medium.

To understand the purpose of man for the planet, one should analyze the process of growth of the body of the planet and its bark, which is moved away from the growing body according to the same law as the trunk of a tree and its bark grow, separated by a thin layer of cambium, which simultaneously generates cells of the trunk and bark.

The thin layer of asthenosphere between the planetary body and the planet's crust appears to play the same role for the planet as the cambium layer does for a tree. Moving away from the body, the bark cracks, a lot of heat is released in the fractures, and the wounds need to be "healed."

The main refrigerator that limits the temperature rise in places where the crust breaks is carbon, turning into hydrocarbons in these places. Being a coolant (compare the same role of carbon in the form of graphite columns in nuclear reactors of nuclear power plants), carbon and its hydrocarbon derivatives do not allow further growth of the crust in these places, and the growth of the planet must continue according to the law of its evolution.

Man and the entire biosphere are hydrocarbon systems, and therefore their role is the same as that of hydrocarbons in the planet's crust - to restrain heating by participating in the carbon cycle.

In the dynamics of the growth of the crust of a planetary body, it is necessary to remove hydrocarbons from its faults, and for this purpose, a whole series of hydrocarbon biological creatures is built, a typical "food series" or the main sequence of living hydrocarbon creatures, each subsequent organism regulates the number of the previous ones.

The top of the hydrocarbon series at the moment is man, endowed with the ability to develop the mind through knowledge of the laws of nature in order to extract hydrocarbons from the planet's crust, ensuring further growth of the crust.

Man, being the most complex hydrocarbon system, lives exclusively on the food range of biological hydrocarbon individuals, including oil, gas, coal and shale. During his life, a person accumulates a certain amount of radioactive carbon C14.

All life in the Universe begins with radiation and ends with it when the reproduction of genetic memory is completed. This is also evidenced by the increase in carbon-14 in the human body. By extracting and destroying hydrocarbons, a person violates the environment, which threatens him with death or great troubles. Therefore, a good deed for the benefit of the Earth must be done wisely.

Thus, the entire biosystem with man at its head serves to solve the main task of the evolution of the planet - they all participate in the general process of controlling the transition of the Earth to the state of a star. It is the evolution of stars that carries out the second phase of reproduction of a copy of the genome of the Universe - it provides the new genome with new sources of energy.

A migrating space tribe of people takes part in a grandiose event - stars are lit from planetary bodies. At the same time, people are obliged to preserve their spiritual essence in the purity of knowledge and direct their entire lives towards this.

Thank you.